

Entrepreneur and Entrepreneurship

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ABSTRACT

This paper traces the historical concept of entrepreneurship to the formal work of Schumpeter. The purpose of this paper is to introduce the formation of entrepreneurship, its development, and transformation into a formal corporate business. We assert that an entrepreneur is one who pays know cost in order to produce income that is uncertain and unfixed. Both uncertainty and unfixed income entails risk; thus, entrepreneurs are commonly called risk takers. However, to limit the definition of entrepreneur to risk taking is incorrect because an entrepreneur truly is someone who defines and redefines, by means of innovation, factors of production and market for consumption. Viewing entrepreneurship in an organizational developmental context, successful entrepreneur builds the enterprise into a family business. Success family business builds itself into a firm, and ultimately formalizes itself into a corporation. The structural formality of the corporate structure sometimes deters entrepreneurs to grow beyond a family business. This is the reason why a family business stays within the family. The entrepreneurial spirit in the individual does not die, and it refuses to succumb to the organizational structure and its structural constraint. An organization that allows the individual free spirit to roam free tends to maintain its competitive edge by effectively combining the benefits of a formal structure, i.e. credibility and access to finance in the formal economy, with the free spirit of the entrepreneur CEO.

Keyword: entrepreneur, entrepreneurship

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

The over all objective of this book is to construct a functional model to explain the inception of a *family business*. The obvious point to start is the entrepreneur and entrepreneurship. After all, family business is the extension of an entrepreneur engaging an enterprise for purposes of increasing economic output. To that end, the learning objective of this Chapter is to introduce the definition of an entrepreneur (the person) and entrepreneurship (the enterprise). In so doing, the reader would have a clearer picture of an entrepreneur as a person, and his/her work: entrepreneurship. The Chapter draws on historical definition and cases to paint a clearer picture of an entrepreneur. Entrepreneurship theory is an off spring of microeconomics. As such, it comes from varied tradition depending on its authorship. From classical economics perspectives, Richard

Cantillon and Adam Smith were the chief authors in the field in the 17th and 18th centuries. Their entrepreneurship was propounded in the tradition of microeconomics. The earlier part of the 20th century, the definition of entrepreneurship was provided by European writers, such as Carl Menger, Ludwig von Mises, Frederick von Hayek and Joseph Schumpeter. Both American and European writers seem to agree that an entrepreneur is the focal point of business success. The success of firms also depend on the individual entrepreneur by extension because the firm is the outgrowth of the *informality* often found among entrepreneurs to codified the “jack-of-all trade” into a more structured environment after the entrepreneur gained some success in the enterprise.

An entrepreneur is the person; entrepreneurship is the enterprise in which the entrepreneurial person engages. The enterprise is engaged in for profit. In so doing, the entrepreneur innovates (Schumpeter, 2012), and takes risks (Knight, 2002) in hope of profitable returns. From nothing more than an idea, an entrepreneur builds on the idea and from an idea an enterprise comes forth through the risk taking conduct of the entrepreneur. An entrepreneur also sees things of this world and asks of “what they could be?” This vision for the possibility of ‘things,’ that do not now exist, motivates the entrepreneur to ‘innovate.’ Into this innovation, efforts, resources, and dedication are spent with the objective of making profits; from this enterprise comes forth new a new frontier in the fields of business and social entrepreneurship (Mair *et al.*, 2006). Note that the objective of the entrepreneur is to make profit whereas the objective of the firm, a more formalized structure of the enterprise, is profit maximization. The idea of profit maximization comes from the fiduciary that the corporate executives owed to the shareholder. However, in the case of an entrepreneur he/she is the stakeholder, a sole proprietor of the enterprise. For basic discussion on legal structure of a business (Dewey, 1926).

2.0 ENTREPRENEUR DEFINED

The word “entrepreneur” is French in origin; it means some one who goes in between. An entrepreneur, in the most classical sense, is a broker; it is a person who links buyers to sellers and makes money in the process. The linking two parties together as a go-between gave rise to the term “entrepreneur.” The modern definition of ‘entrepreneur’ is *someone who undertakes an enterprise with an objective of making profit and undertakes risk in the process.*

2.1 One who Pays Known Cost for Uncertain and Unfixed Income

In 1734, Richard Cantillon defined an entrepreneur as a person who has an unfixed income and pays known cost for an uncertain income (Tarascio, 1985). This earlier definition provides a picture of the characteristics of an entrepreneur as an economic agent. *First*, an entrepreneur has unfixed income. The work of an entrepreneur, the enterprise or entrepreneurship, is informal and the environment within which the entrepreneur operates is also informal. An entrepreneur uses his own resources for the production of income. In so doing, an entrepreneur undertakes risk. *Second*, Cantillon states that an entrepreneur pays a known cost. This requisite appears to be troublesome. One thing that an entrepreneur, especially in the 21st century, does is not to pay any costs and makes money from selling ideas; sometimes an entrepreneur pays costs but these costs are uncertain. In fact, most entrepreneurial enterprise involves costs that are not known and unfixed, thus, rendering the nature of an entrepreneur’s work

The third element of Cantillon’s definition of an entrepreneur is that an entrepreneur has an *uncertain income*. This characteristic of an entrepreneur remains true until today. This uncertainty conjures the idea of risk. As someone who lives and works with uncertain income, it can be said that an entrepreneur is a risk taker. In fact, this conjecture later becomes the standard characteristic of an entrepreneur among contemporary writers of the early 20th and 21st centuries. The uncertainty of income production comes from the informality of an entrepreneur’s work environment. A pure entrepreneur is some one who can work with an idea, but without any formal planning. An entrepreneur is not someone who walks around with a business plan and *pro forma* financial statements. An entrepreneur is someone who pays a certain sum with the expectation of profitable

returns. An entrepreneur is a gambler in business. For Cantillon, the entrepreneur's role in society is in microeconomics. An entrepreneur acts for himself. He invests his own money in hope of making profit. Cantillon does not call the expenses an investment; he called it costs. The profit, whatever amount made, is uncertain.

2.2 Unifier of Factors of Production: Land, Labor, Raw Materials, Capital for the Production and Market for the Consumption

In 1803, Jean-Baptiste Say defined the entrepreneur as someone who unifies various factors of production together to produce a product, and thus collect rent (commission or making money from this linking together of buyers, sellers, and laborers) in the process. This definition captures the spirit of the original French concept of the term 'entrepreneur' as some one who 'goes between' two economic agents. Say explains the context in which an entrepreneur works:

“It is worthwhile to remark that a product is no sooner created than it, from that instant, affords a market for other products to the full extent of its own value. When the producer has put the finishing hand to his product, he is most anxious to sell it immediately, lest its value should diminish in his hands. Nor is he less anxious to dispose of the money he may get for it; for the value of money is also perishable. But the only way of getting rid of money is in the purchase of some product or other. Thus the mere circumstance of creation of one product immediately opens a vent for other products.” (J.B. Say, 1803: pp. 138–9).

It is in such macroeconomics context of the economy that an entrepreneur is defined. According to Say, an entrepreneur is an economic agent. An economic agent is someone who acts and interacts with other agents in the economy to produce goods and services, and in the process of exchanging these goods and services or their intermediary, money changes hands. Under this contextual definition, the role of the entrepreneur in the economy is two-folds. On the one hand, an entrepreneur serves as a go-between among owners of factors of production: factory owners, land owners, and laborers, to come together and produce a product. On the other, once that product is produced, the manufacturer also needs to push the product into the market. In fulfilling this need, the entrepreneur also has a further role to play: brokering sales and distribution. These two developments were not recognized by Richard Cantillon who focused almost entirely on the entrepreneur as a private investor in an uncertain enterprise or project with the objective of making profit, and *that profit* is uncertain. However, in Say's treatise, it was pointed out that the entrepreneur does not have to be an investor. An entrepreneur may a go-between brokering deals between owners of factors of production. This match-making role of an entrepreneur defines an entrepreneur as an innovator, not a risk taker.

Under Say's contextual definition of an entrepreneur, an entrepreneur is not a risk taker, but a risk minimizer. Paying known cost for uncertain income, being a risk taker as envisioned by Cantillon, is one perception of an entrepreneur. However, serving as catalyst in the economy by uniting buyers, sellers, and laborers together for the purpose of producing a product helps paint a different picture of an entrepreneur. In Say's portraiture, an entrepreneur is a prototype of an information analyst long before the information age. In order to be successful in matchmaking, the entrepreneur has to be well informed about the sources of labor, land, raw materials and capital. By bringing these factors of production together, the entrepreneur plays a vital role in the economy. Unlike Cantillon confining the entrepreneur to the microeconomics level, Say recognizes the entrepreneur in both microeconomics (brokering the sales and distribution of the product after it has been manufactured), and macroeconomics level (bringing factors of productions together). In such a capacity, the entrepreneur is a resource allocator. He shifts resources from low to high efficiency level. To that end, the entrepreneur plays a vital role in the economy.

2.3 An Entrepreneur is an Innovator of Process, Products, and Services from Existing Resources

From the time of Cantillon in 1734 and Say’s essay in 1803, there lies a span of 69 years, the definition of entrepreneurship started out as a microeconomic agent during the time of Cantillon and attained an additional role as a macroeconomic agent under Say’s contribution. For 131 years, the subject was left untouched. No one attempted to redefine the term ‘entrepreneur’ again until 1934. The intellectual community in Europe seemed to have been intoxicated with two industrial revolutions between 1760-1820 and 1840-1870; no new ideas or additional theoretical contribution had been made until after the first quarter of the 20th century. It was not until 1934 did the Austrian economist, Joseph Alois Schumpeter, breathed new life into the idea. Schumpeter proposed a new definition for an entrepreneur. For Schumpeter, an entrepreneur is an innovator; some one who uses existing resources and produce something completely new or improved products or services. An entrepreneur is some one who shatters the confine of an existing order.

In defining an entrepreneur as an innovator, Schumpeter introduces the concept of creative destruction. Schumpeter argues that advances in technologies came about as the result of innovative spirit among entrepreneurs. Even when a firm invents something, the innovation mostly came as the result of the innovative efforts of the entrepreneurs inside the firm. As new and better products are introduced, old ones are replaced or shelved. This technological obsolescence was called *creative destruction*. For Schumpeter, creative destruction was the key to breaking new frontiers in basic and applied sciences; the application of the new found knowledge was spearheaded by entrepreneurs in the organization or by entrepreneurs themselves.

During the time of Schumpeter, innovation was loosely defined. It was loosely defined as something ‘new;’ as well as improvement. However, this untidy definition confuses innovation with invention. New discovery defines an invention. Innovation is the application or reuse of existing resources for better result. Despite the untidy definition of innovation, under Schumpeter’s new vision of an entrepreneur, an entrepreneur is both an inventor and innovator. As an inventor, the entrepreneur introduces new products, services or process *never before* existed. This introduction of new products, services or process into the economy reaffirms Say’s conception of the role of the entrepreneur: active in microeconomics and macroeconomics. As an innovator, Schumpeter recognizes the drive and energy of an entrepreneur who, either out of necessity or creativity, breaths new life into the economic process.

Schumpeter’s creative destruction must be read in its historical context. October 29, 1929 saw the stock market crash in the US (Frank and Benmark, 2007). Black Tuesday, as it was later called, signaled a world wide great economic depression. It lasted until the mid 1940s. The effect of the Great Depression was felt throughout the West. England, France and Germany were adversely affected by it.

Table 1: Change in Economic Indicator among major economies of the world during the great Depression: 1929-1932.

	<i>United States</i>	<i>Great Britain</i>	<i>France</i>	<i>Germany</i>
Industrial production	-46%	-23%	-24%	-41%
Wholesale prices	-32%	-33%	-34%	-29%
Foreign trade	-70%	-60%	-54%	-61%
Unemployment	+607%	+129%	+214%	+232%

Source: Jerome Blum, Rondo Cameron, Thomas G. Barnes (1970). *The European world: a history* (2nd ed.), p. 885.

The introduction of the idea of innovation in Schumpeter's writing in 1934 came out of an economic milieu as shown in Table 1.0. Europe's industrial production fell from the low of negative 23% in England to the high of negative 41% in Germany. The inventiveness talked by Schumpeter might not have come from inventive spirit, but it came from the weight economic desperation and by the force of necessity for advanced economies to break itself from the stagnation of the economic depression. Germany's unemployment rate rose by 232% and 607% in the US between 1929 and 1932s; under this condition, the entrepreneur would have access to resources that would have otherwise been denied to him, i.e. capital infrastructure. This condition may have provided the impetus for creative destruction referred to by Schumpeter.

2.4 Higher Achiever, Risk Taker and Opportunity Seeker

After Schumpeter, attempts to paint the picture of an entrepreneur were less fruitful. Some authors, such as Peter Druker sees an entrepreneur as someone who looks for change and exploits opportunities. An entrepreneur is a person who takes a source and turns it into a resource through innovation. This attempt to redefine the term "entrepreneur" does not do any better than what Schumpeter had done. In 1961, Michael McClelland wrote that an entrepreneur is a high achiever (McClelland, 1978). This attempt to define an entrepreneur is argumentative. Many entrepreneurs are driven by necessity more than the needs for personal achievement. In most developing economies, street vendors would qualify to be called entrepreneurs; however, these people are not high achiever in any sense of the term: achievement. Street vendors sell on the streets because they want to make a living; their job was chosen out of necessity. If they have other options, they would rather own a company and product products that would earn them more money. However, such is not the case. Therefore, it cannot be said that being a high achiever is a requisite for being an entrepreneur. If personal character is an element to define an entrepreneur, *resilience and persistency* are more appropriate. Resilience refers to the ability to adapt to changing circumstances. Like the entrepreneur in the Cantillon world, the individual entrepreneur is but a speck of dot in the over all macroeconomy. This is particularly true for the entrepreneur selling consumer goods on the sidewalk pavement. He pays certain cost and earns uncertain income. Rain or sun, he has no choice but to stand and sell his wares on the pavement. Is he high achiever? No, he is not. He is on the street selling products because he has no choice. It is dictated to him by the necessity of life. However, is he less entrepreneur than someone who creates an iPhone? The answer is 'no.' Both a man selling noodle soup on the street to make a living and someone creating a iPhone in a sophisticated laboratory possess the same characteristic: flexibility to change in circumstances. An iPhone creator must respond to changes in the market and technological trends; so too must the man on the street adapt himself to changes in his circumstances, such as changing price of his noodle soup in response to the increasing price of raw materials.

A second character that McClelland failed to appreciate in an entrepreneur is persistency. An entrepreneur is someone who does not quit. This is often mistaken for a high level of desire to achieve. A closer examination of an entrepreneur shows that most entrepreneurs have been involved in more than one products or enterprise. The changing of enterprise shows that (i) *an entrepreneur is an opportunity seeker, and (ii) in face of failure, the entrepreneur recognizes and accepts the failure and move on to a different enterprise.* When selling noodle soup fails, an entrepreneur moves on selling different products but still retains his character of being his own boss, taking risk, exploits opportunities that comes his way, and getting himself up and running as soon as he realizes that he had fallen. This may not be said that this character shows that an entrepreneur is a high achiever. It shows that the entrepreneur is persistent in earning his living. The different between a high achiever and an entrepreneur is that a high achiever does not accept failure and is unwilling to accept failure. However, an entrepreneur is too willing to accept failure by recognizing that the resources spent on the project or enterprise did not produce the profit he anticipated. He sooner recognizes the failure; he closes that chapter of his trial-and-error and move on to newer and more exciting projects.

An entrepreneur is an *opportunity seeker*. This term needs to be defined. An opportunity seeker is not the same as an opportunist. An opportunist is one who takes opportunities of others. The issue of ethics becomes an issue in the discussion of opportunist. The term opportunist always carries a negative connotation. An opportunity seeker is someone who undertakes calculated risk with the objective of profitable within bounds of reason. This is the difference between a truant or a thief and a self-employed business person. An entrepreneur engages in business; in so doing, he seeks opportunity to improve his lot in society without alienating those from whom he profit. Fair bargaining is the rule by which an entrepreneur follows. To that end, he is an opportunity seeker, not an opportunist. Lying and cheating are not the character of an entrepreneur. An entrepreneur is some one who is in business for himself. His gain comes through a process that benefits those with whom he does business.

2.5 Risk Taking without Regards to Availability of Resources

Risk is defined as uncertainty. Uncertainty is the lack of definite knowledge whether the event will occur. This broad definition allows risk to encompass positive and negative effect resulted from uncertainty. Certain types of risk may result in the increase in value of assets held. For instance, the increase in value of a currency leads to the increase in value of the portfolio holding that currency. The opposite may also be true when the currency becomes weaker, the portfolio holding that currency leads to decrease in portfolio value. In the context of risk taking by an entrepreneur, both aspects of risk apply. It is erroneous to define risk only as a possible loss; the possibility of gain is also considered as risk, if that possibility is uncertain.

An entrepreneur is a risk taker. Generally, in business, a business person takes risk by investing his resources or money in a certain project. However, an entrepreneur takes risk regardless of the availability of resources. In the most extreme case, an entrepreneur has nothing to gamble with except his good name and the idea to which he clings. To that end, there are no known resources, such as money of assets, which an entrepreneur make put up as the stake in the game. To that end, an entrepreneur is a risk taker regardless of the availability of resources, except *time*, *talents* and *tolerance*. An entrepreneur has *time*. His time is value and could be equated to money. With this mental construct, an entrepreneur trains himself to be time sensitive in all the tasks and activities undertaken by him. He demands timeliness for himself and those with whom he deals. An entrepreneur has *talents* to be multitasked. He is a jack-of-all trade, and an expert of none. These talents allow him to think, reflect and act in all activities that present opportunities for gains. The talents of an entrepreneur are indicative of his character which is imprinted into his personality and traits. For that reason, it is difficult to learn to be an entrepreneur. However, this is not to say that entrepreneurial character is beyond decipherable. The talents of an entrepreneur may be learned and emulated. Lastly, an entrepreneur generally has higher level of *tolerance* towards risk than a common person who seeks the certainty of a regular employment. While most people cannot stand uncertainty, an entrepreneur strives in face of uncertainty. The combination of these three personal assets: time, talents and tolerance, allows an entrepreneur to triumph in face of uncertainty. An entrepreneur can risk the loss of time because time is renewable in that there is always a “tomorrow” waiting to bring the daylight anew. An entrepreneur can risk his talents because talents cannot be lost; with each enterprise he undertakes, an entrepreneur sharpens his skills and hones his talents to a more robust standing. Lastly, an entrepreneur has higher level of tolerance towards risk, and, therefore, can benefits from it when other would shirk away. These personal “assets” are non-quantifiable. To that end, it is said that an entrepreneur is a risk taker regards of the availability of resources. Without money, an entrepreneur can still put his time, talents and tolerance at risk; at the end, he may triumph.

There is a limitation on the magnitude and type of risk taken by an entrepreneur because the risk taken by an entrepreneur is regardless of the availability of resources. For that reason, the type and magnitude of risk taken by the entrepreneur is called calculated risk. A calculated risk is an undertaking embarked upon only after weighing all possible outcomes. In addition, not all risks may

be taken by an entrepreneur. Although it is said that the risk taken by the entrepreneur is regardless of the availability of resources, it only means that the ratio of potential loss over assets on hand may be higher than the degree of risk exposure undertaken by a firm. An entrepreneur can risk one hundred percent of his assets; however, a firm may not be as reckless. “Recklessness” is acting with substantial knowledge of the adverse consequence. A firm may not act with a substantial knowledge of the potential loss for a firm is bound by fiduciary to stakeholders and the decision process must be transparent to all stakeholders. The entrepreneur, on the other hand, is not answer to anyone except himself. As a final arbiter of his own action, an entrepreneur is at liberty to act. However, his conduct is circumscribed by how much he could afford to lose. For an entrepreneur, his risk tolerance may be as high as putting all his stakes at the table in one betting in hope that he will gain in return. This is the type of character that allows Cantillon to define an entrepreneur as someone who pays a known cost for the opportunity to earn an uncertain income. The limitation of an entrepreneur’s risk is his stake in the game. Beyond what he owns, and risk what he does not own, an entrepreneur ceases to be a businessman and transforms himself to nothing more than a common gambler. An entrepreneur gambles in a sense that he bets for the hope to gain more than what he possesses by investing in uncertainty. However, this gambling is not compulsive, it is guided by reason. The reason that guides an entrepreneur not to bet on every thing that he owns allow the entrepreneur to retain the sanity of a reasonable person. To be something less, i.e. a common gambler, would lead to the destruction of an entrepreneur’s credibility and ultimately his downfall in society. An entrepreneur, unlike a corporation selling a product with branding, sells the product that is branded by his personal credibility. Credibility is the good will that an entrepreneur could not afford to lose. Attempts had been made by many writers to define the term “entrepreneur;” despite the changes in the definition throughout history, one thing seems unchanged: an entrepreneur plays an active role in microeconomics and macroeconomics. An entrepreneur makes the economy going; he shakes the world and the industry in which his enterprise touches. ‘Making’ and ‘shaking’ the world is the hallmark of an entrepreneur.

3.0 ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEFINED

Entrepreneurship is defined as the undertaking by an entrepreneur with the object of making profits or increase economic output regardless of resources currently controlled (Reynolds, 1997). The undertaking is called an enterprise. An enterprise is an activity engaged in for profit. It should be noted that the term “profit” should be broadly described as an increase in economic benefits. Modernly, the entrepreneurship benefits both the entrepreneur and society. There are many types of entrepreneurship: social entrepreneurship (Abu-Saifan, 2012; Mair et al., 2006; Peredo and McLean, 2006; and Elkington and Hartigan, 2008), political entrepreneurship (Cohen, 2012; Choi, 2004), or knowledge entrepreneurship (Kanter, 1983; Lumpkin and Dess, 1996; Mason, 2001; McDonald, 2002; Kuratko, 2006). The conduct of the entrepreneur in the enterprise is characterized by two elements: (i) risk taking and (ii) innovation.

Schumpeter wrote that entrepreneurship is the taking of existing or new invention to produce innovation (Schumpeter, 2012). Innovation is the use of existing resources to produce additional output through the application of better process, process or method. This additional output may be called increased productivity or X-efficiency (Stigler; 1976; Leibenstein, 1996; 2008), or maintaining the same level of output but reduce the level of input; in another word, increase output with the same level of input. Entrepreneurship in the 21st century entails the use of existing resources to improve productivity or increase efficiency.

3.1 Entrepreneurship as Risk Taking Enterprise

The taking of risk is the hallmark of entrepreneurship. The objective of the enterprise is clear: with known cost, an entrepreneur engages an enterprise in order to increase the economic output from that enterprise. In so doing, the enterprise develops and grows. In the alternative, since not all enterprises are successful, the enterprise may fail.

For an entrepreneur, a fail enterprise is value. To an academic, failure has no value. In order to understand entrepreneurship, both success and failure of entrepreneurship must be studied. Success story in entrepreneurship can be seen every where; however, for every successful story there hundreds more of failed attempts in entrepreneurial activities. However, failed stories are not celebrated. This turning away from failed stories has made progress in research in entrepreneurship slow to progress. The success stories of Bill Gate of Microsoft, Steve Jobs of Apple or Mark Zucker of Facebook are commoditized stories of personal success in entrepreneurship. What can the world learn from these people and their enterprises? Practically nothing. If we seek to understand the success of entrepreneurship, it is necessary to learn how entrepreneurship failed.

We live in a society that does not celebrate failure. Our value system shuns failure; therefore, we lack the capacity to learn from our mistakes. However, one key factor to success in entrepreneurship is that a successful enterprise is but upon many failed projects. The successful entrepreneur tells the stories of his success in one enterprise, but he does not divulge his failure in many projects that leads to that success. This secrecy is part of the secret of success in entrepreneurship. Failure in entrepreneurship is the least explored area of research in entrepreneurship. For that reason, progress in research in entrepreneurship, and by extension the management theories and philosophy for family business, is slow. Schumpeter, for instance, talks about innovation as a key to entrepreneurship and the success of an entrepreneur; however, Schumpeter himself does not seem to appreciate the fact that every successful innovation is but one story built upon hundreds of failed stories.

If entrepreneurship is the act of taking risk, it is too incredulous to believe that all risk taking enterprises lead to success. A success is but one of many untold tales. How then can we discover failed stories in order to avoid the pitfalls in entrepreneurship? In order to learn from failure, people who failed must be willing to share the stories of their failure. However, this is not probable because human society places greater value on success and shuns those who failed. However, failure is the building block for entrepreneurial success. A family business, for instance, starts its life in business from an entrepreneurial enterprise of a single person. It is only if the entrepreneur becomes successful will the success be shared with the family members and the enterprise is transformed into a family business. A failed entrepreneurship never gets the opportunity to become a family business. This simple observation reaffirms the idea of *risk taking* in entrepreneurship. By engaging in an enterprise, the entrepreneur takes risk. In order to minimize the risk, as part of risk management, the entrepreneur does not share the risk with anyone in the family except confine the risk to the enterprise and himself. This fact seems antithetical to mainstream theory in risk management which advocates the spreading and sharing of risk in order to lessen the effect of risk upon the agent. Although this theoretical assertion seems plausible, it does not play out in entrepreneurship and family business.

A second challenge against learning from failure in entrepreneurship is the unwillingness in knowledge sharing. Failed entrepreneurs are not willing to share information about their failure. Although they are ready to share the stories of their success, entrepreneurs are not as vocal in their stories of failing in many enterprises from which they gather and build experience which leads to their success. This lack of knowledge sharing prevents knowledge from being diffused into the entrepreneurial community. Thus, other entrepreneurs may repeat the same mistakes over and again in the same and similar enterprises. To that end, entrepreneurship, despite the gloating success of the likes of Bill Gate, Steve Jobs and Mark Zuckerberg, is quite inefficient in resource management. In a more formal setting, such as a firm or corporation, failed stories are recorded, shared and diffused within the firm and the industry. Failure is not repeated; efficiency in resource allocation may also be achieved through shared knowledge. In entrepreneurship, resource management is not as efficient. The inefficiency in entrepreneurship may be due to the fact that all entrepreneurial activities are conducted within an informal structure.

The informality of entrepreneurship creates additional risk. The enterprise has an inherent risk; in additional, the way in which an entrepreneurship is carried out also produces risk. This

additional risk cannot be eliminated, and it is also difficult to manage because the lack of organizational structure in entrepreneurship means that managerial efficiency is lacking. This risk becomes less pronounced when the entrepreneurship is diffused to other family members. Family members of an entrepreneur do not share the risk of an entrepreneur. It is only after an entrepreneur is successful do family members show the willingness to engage the enterprise. Again this shows that the failed experience or knowledge is not shared. Therefore, the study of a family business must begin with the study of an entrepreneur and his enterprise.

3.2 Entrepreneurship as Innovative Enterprise

In 1930s, Schumpeter claims that innovation is the hallmark of entrepreneurship. Innovation is defined as the use of existing resources to make something better or use existing input to increase productivity. Innovation is closely related to knowledge. As an enterprise, entrepreneurship is an informal organization possessing disorganized and informal knowledge. Knowledge is defined as the body of unprocessed data, facts, and a state of cognition possess by the individual or organization. In entrepreneurship, the entrepreneur is the individual. The enterprise is a semi-organization. It is not a fully functional organization because an enterprise operated by the entrepreneur is without structure.

Innovation is the use of existing knowledge to increase productivity. Entrepreneurship is unstructured or semi-structure. Without a formal organizational structure, entrepreneurship may have greater freedom to be innovative. Innovation depends on creativity. Creativity is defined as the expression of inventive spirit in the person. This expression may be in the form of idea or ideas manifested on form and function. In the context of entrepreneurship, innovation may come forth more readily because an entrepreneur is not constrained by the organizational structure. Entrepreneurship, for that reason, Schumpeter reasoned that is the cradle of innovation. The free spirit of an entrepreneur engages in innovation without structure hindrance of the organizational constraint.

As an individual, an entrepreneur can be innovative. This part is easily understood by the fact that an entrepreneur does not answer to anyone, but himself. As an enterprise, how can entrepreneurship be innovative since it is not structured? It appears to be contradictory that an “enterprise” is unstructured. It is considered unstructured because it lacks the formal organization of a corporate business. As an activity conceived and operated by an individual (entrepreneur), it can be called an enterprise. This enterprise is a one man show; for that reason, an entrepreneurship is an enterprise and is not structured. As such, it is an innovative enterprise by extension of the fact that the individual entrepreneur running the enterprise is innovative.

What is innovation? Innovation is defined as the improvement of the current system which does not require additional investment. There are two types of innovation: *input innovation* and *performance innovation*. Input innovation refers to the reduction of cost in order to maintain the same or higher level of output. Output innovation or performance innovation refers to the increase in output with the same level of input. Under this two-prong definition, how can an entrepreneurship be an innovative enterprise? Recall Cantillon’s definition of an entrepreneur as someone who pays a ‘known cost for uncertain income.’ This statement is half true. An entrepreneur pays a known cost. However, the income or output of the enterprise is anticipated. That anticipated amount has a point of reference. At minimum, the expected income must exceed the initial investment otherwise the enterprise would operate at a loss. The amount of earning, i.e. output or performance may not be ascertainable with an exact figure, but whatever it is, it must exceed an initial investment. An entrepreneur has a point of reference as how much the returns for the investment should be. However, what is lacking is the hurdle rate for the return which an entrepreneur must benchmark against the standard rate of return. This is a problem because an entrepreneur and his enterprise lack a point of reference. Entrepreneurship is an individual enterprise. The enterprise is unorganized. Therefore, there is no such a thing as an *industry standard* in entrepreneurship. How then can an enterprise be innovative if innovation is a quantitative

comparison of a subject event to a known observation? The answer to this question lies in the inextricability of an entrepreneur and the enterprise.

If the entrepreneur is innovative then the enterprise is by default innovative because they are not separable. The true question then is ‘whether the entrepreneur is innovative?’ An entrepreneur is a person who uses the existing *source* by turning it into *resource*. This is another definition of innovation. The enterprise becomes innovative when the entrepreneur inputs his energy, creativity, and resources to produce greater output. The resource without the action of the entrepreneur or without putting the enterprise into motion is *stationary*, i.e. idle or nonproductive. The enterprise puts the resources in motion and, thus, produces an output from an otherwise idle resource or asset. This logic provides the answer to the original query requiring innovation to have a benchmarking standard. The enterprise benchmarks itself against a non-productive asset; by turning that asset into a product resource, innovation occurs. In this case, the standard is a measurement of any output against a stationary point: zero productivity. Therefore, any output of an enterprise, as long as it is non-negative, is an innovation.

4.0 CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have laid the foundation of the most basic unit of business enterprise: an entrepreneur. Moreover, the life and work of an entrepreneur is expected to develop through a life cycle. An entrepreneur starts out with one activity; if he fails, he accepts that failure and move on to the next seemingly profitable activity. If the activity is successful, he would build upon it until it becomes an enterprise. From this portrait of the entrepreneur’s work, we noted that an activity must be successful in order to become an enterprise. A successful enterprise is one that is innovative. Innovation has been defined as the use of existing resources to increase the current level of productivity. Productivity increase is benchmarked against a set standard. It has been posited in this chapter that idled assets has zero productivity. An entrepreneur injects the idled asset into his enterprise and thus transforms the asset from zero productivity to positive productivity. Success of the enterprise leads to growth; this growth is a growth within an enterprise that is without formal structure. Therefore, the most natural target for the spill over is the family. Family business is a natural development of a successful enterprise of an entrepreneur. An entrepreneur is a risk taker; however, the risk affinity of the entrepreneur is limited to what he has at stake. He cannot lose what he does not have nor can he afford to expose the risk of his enterprise to those around him. For this reason, an entrepreneur absorbs his risk and would involve the family members, i.e. allowing the enterprise to grow into a family business, only when the enterprise becomes successful. We may classify the success of the entrepreneur as a first degree of success; the success of the family business as a second degree; and, if the family business transforms itself into SME, a third degree of success. Success leads to growth; growth leads to the implementation of formal structure. The formality of an organization constrains the free spirit of an entrepreneur whose free spirit always yearn to break free from the organizational constraint. For that reason,

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